

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF DERIVATIVE WORDS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

Morphology and Semantics

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Abstract

This article provides semantic analysis of word structure and construction. The meaning of the derivative word has been studied on the basis of sememe, *seme* and *ema*. The possibilities of polysemantic morphemes in word formation are illuminated. An analysis of the formation of artificial words based on semantics is given. It is based on the fact that the meaning of a word has basic and peripheral semantics and that it is important to pay attention to these semantics when studying artificial words by the method of semantic analysis. The semantic and polysemous lexemes of word formation are described. The formation of polysemous lexemes was determined on the basis of each semaphore of polysemous lexemes. The semantic structure of artificial words is studied on the basis of the method of component analysis. The meaning of compound words is analyzed on the basis of *sememe*, *seme*, *ema*. The formation of compound words based on lexemes, sememas, and semantics has been studied. Based on the semantics of polysemous morphemes, the formation of compound words with different meanings has been identified. The formation of lexical units on the basis of free compound (phrase), fixed compound (phrase) and the transition of a sentence to a compound word have been analyzed analytically, and the distinctive features of these units are explained on the basis of semantic, syntactic analysis.

In Uzbek linguistics, such scientists as A.Gulamov, A.Khojiev, R.Kungurov, M.Mirtojiev conducted scientific research on artificial words. The abundance of work on word formation indicates that these issues have been sufficiently studied in linguistics. Due to the semantic development of language units, the richness of the Uzbek language in polysemantic words, it is necessary to study the semantic structure of artificial words.

Some word-forming suffixes have multiple meanings. The semantic side of suffixes is represented by semantics, and these semantics affect word semantics. The suffix *-li* is a polysemous morpheme with the semantics "have" and "many". The word *suvli* has the semantics "there is water" and "there is a lot of water". In the aqueous compound, the suffix *-li* represents the semaphore, and in the aquatic peach compound, the suffix "many". Also, polysemous suffixes are formed as a result of the polysemous lexeme acting as an affix. M., the word *xo'r* is peculiar to the Persian-Tajik languages and has the semantics "eat something", "drink something", and on the basis of these semantics the words *nonxo'r*, *choyxo'r* are formed. For example, the *nonxo'r* has the sememe "bread-eater", the *choyxo'r* has the sememe "tea-drinker". The suffix *-xo'r* in these lexemes is a polysemous suffix. The occurrence of the phenomenon of enantiosema is observed within the semes of the polysemous appendix. M., the suffix *-chang* in the lexeme of the pistol represents the antonyms "yes" and "no".

So word-forming suffixes can be singular or plural. Polysemy occurs not within semantics, but within semantics. Therefore, the term polysemous cannot be applied to polysemous additions. It would be correct to think of them as polysemous (multi-semantic) additions.

Depending on the structure of the word semantics, it is in the form of a phrase or a sentence. The semantics that express the main meaning in the semantics are the dominant semantics, and the semantics that explain it are the subordinate semantics. The semantics of the *gulchilik* (English meaning: engaging in flower growing) lexeme is expressed in the form of a phrase. For example, while the semantics “activity” and “profession” in the semantics of “florist’s activity, profession” are dominant semantics, the semantics of “*gulchi*” are subordinate semantics. In the dominant part of the semantics of the artificial word there are semantics representing word-forming adverbs, and in the subordinate part there are semantics representing the core. In the process of word formation, both the semantics in the dominant part and the semantics in the subordinate part change. In this sense, each artificial word has its own semantic structure. The study of the semantic structure of a compound word requires an analysis of semantics, semantics, and eme. For example, the semantics of *gulchilik* (florist's activity, profession) has a subordinate semantic “*gulchi*” (a person engaged in flower growing). This seme has “gul” (flower), “ekuvchi” (planter), “shaxs” (person), of which *gul* (flower) is not “red”, “white”, “blooming” in “colors”, “leafy”, “root” and “plant”.

Compound words are formed on the basis of lexemes and polysemous lexemes on the basis of a specific sememe, i.e. the core of a compound word consists of a lexeme or sememe. It is known that the figurative meaning (sememe) of a word is formed on the basis of metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, function. These tools are important in understanding the meaning of artificial words. M., artificial words are formed on the basis of the following semantics of the main polysemous lexeme: 1. Correct meaning (sememe): *boshli* (has a head); 2. The figurative meaning (sememe):

a) The figurative meaning (sememe) formed on the basis of the metaphor will be the leading morpheme: *boshloq* (bosh + loq). Formed on the basis of simulation according to its location at the top of the head;

b) on the basis of metonymy: *boshsiz* (bosh + siz). The main morpheme represented the semantic "mind." A portable meaning was formed because the concept of mind had another connection;

c) on the basis of synecdoche: *boshpana* (bosh + pana). The main morpheme has the seme “man”. By saying the name of the part, its inherent meaning is understood;

d) on the basis of duties: *boshliq* (bosh + liq). Based on the management function of the head, such a sememe emerged.

Thus, the method of semantic analysis should be used in the study of the meaning and methods of formation of artificial words. The role of sememe, sema, ema is great in distinguishing morphemes and studying their semantic connection, in determining the semantic structure of a

word. Determining the formation of polysemous lexemes on the basis of specific semantics or potential semantics is important in the analysis of word structure.

It is known that the semantics of a word consists of denotative, connotative semantics. For example, the **chehra** (face) lexeme has denotative and “positive” connotative semantics such as “man”, “head”, “front”, “side”. These are the basic (explicit, explicit) semantics, and the peripheral (hidden) semantics of the lexeme are also present. The basis for the emergence of peripheral semantics is:

1. Peripheral semantics arise on the basis of the connection of a word to a word, that is, as a result of the formation of a figurative meaning. For example, in the combination of **oltinodam** (golden man), the word **oltin** represents the semantics “equal, unparalleled”.

2. Peripheral semantics arise in connection with a particular speech situation, the process of communication. For example, the semantic **soyabon** (umbrella) semantic characteristic of the rain lexeme can be realized by saying that it is raining towards a person.

3. Based on the phenomenon of ellipsis, the lexeme sememe expands with certain semantics. For example, words in the adjective category also represent the noun's "person" and "thing" semantics. For example, while good people often have the semantic “positive trait” in their speech, **yaxshiodamlarko‘p** (good people are many) have the semantics of “positive”, “trait” and “personality”.

4. The hidden sema in a lexeme arises on the basis of an addition to that lexeme. M., **thexotin** (female) semantic characteristic of the **bo‘y** (height) lexeme, occurs when the suffix **-doq** is added to this lexeme. The **bo‘ydoq** (unmarried) lexeme has the meaning of “unmarried.” The **uy** (house) lexeme also has the semantic “wife”, which is also formed when the suffixes **-la**, **-im** are added to this lexeme. For example, the word **uylanmoq** (to marry) means “to take a wife,” and the word **o‘yim** means “wife.”

5. Certain semantics arise on the basis of the opposite use of words. For example, the “easy” semantics of the word **aytish** (to say), the **qiyin** (“difficult”) semantics of the word **qilish** (to do), occur on the basis of semantic contrast of lexemes. For example, **aytishoson, qilishqiyin** (*easy to say, hard to do*) (proverb). Since the semantics of **oson** (easy) in the word utterance existed in secret, it emerged when the word **aytish** (to say) was an antonym of the word **qilish** (to do).

Lexeme semantics are divided into denotative and potential semantics according to their explicit and implicit expression. Denotative semantics form the noun (lexical) meaning of a word. Potential semantics, on the other hand, occur under certain speech conditions. Derivative and figurative meanings of polysemous words usually arise on the basis of semantics (more, denotative, potential semantics) in the main meaning. Almost all meanings of polysemous words are the basis for the formation of artificial words. Sh.Rahmatullaev considers each meaning in polysemous words as a separate language unit and calls these meanings by the term sememe [8, p. 79]. Artificial words are formed on the basis of lexemes, sememes, and semantics. In particular, compound words are also made on the basis of such units.

In Uzbek linguistics the lexical and morphological features of compound words are sufficiently studied [1]. The study of their semantic structure by the method of semantic analysis is important in the study of the role and participation of semantics and semantics in word formation. It is known that the composition of compound words consists of two or more morphemes. Morphemes differ in their singularity or plurality. There are many polysemous morphemes in Uzbek language. They have many semantic and multi-semantic types. For example, morphemes such as **poya**, **noma**, **talab** (haulm, noma, demand) are plural and implement different semantics in a compound word. For example, the **poya** (haulm) morpheme denotes the semantic **novda** (rod) in the word **g'o'zapoya** (cotton stalk), and in the correct sense; The word **zinapoya** (staircase) means the **poya** (step), and the word "step" means "place" and participates in word formation with the meaning of the product **bedapoya**, **sholipoya**. Compound words are formed on the basis of the interconnection of morphemes with head, derivative, portable meaning. For example:

1. All morphemes in some compound words are combined on the basis of the correct (main) meaning: *kamhosil*, *kamquvvat*, *ko'kqarg'a tog'olcha*.

2. The first part of some compound words is figurative, the second part is literal. For example, the royal part of the word **shohbayt**(rhyme line) is in a figurative sense and is attached to the **bayt** morpheme in the semantics of “the best, yellow of something or someone”.

3. The first part of some compound words is in the literal sense; the second part is in the figurative sense. For example, the part of the **tirnoq** (claw) in the **qo'shtirnoq** (quotation mark) is used in a figurative sense.

4. All parts of some compound words consist of morphemes with portable meanings. For example, the **bosh** (main) part of the word **boshqotirma** (puzzle) is figurative and has the semantics of “mind, brain”, and the **qotmoq** (to solidify) part represents the semantics of “hard thinking, thinking” in the figurative sense.

Polysemous lexemes (other than the main sememe) are named after the semantics. The combination of nomema and sememe can be natural or conditional. A unit formed on the basis of a natural combination is a lexeme (word). The unit formed by conditional aggregation is called sememe [3, p. 24]. Accordingly, the compound word structure has the following lexical-semantic structure:

1. Lexeme + lexeme: *kamhosil*, *kamquvvat*
2. Sememe + lexeme: *shohbayt*.
3. Lexeme + sememe: *qo'shtirnoq*.
4. Sememe + sememe: *tilyog'lama*.

Sememe as a unit of speech is a derivative of polysemous lexemes, an expression of portable meanings. It is well known that portable meaning usually arises on the basis of metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, function. Accordingly, the compound word structure is analyzed as follows:

1. A compound word contains a semantics based on a metaphor. For example, the first part of the word **karnaygul** (trumpet) is based on resemblance. The word **karnaygul** means “a creeping plant and its trumpet-shaped flower”/The meaning of this compound word is abbreviated as “trumpet-like flower” semantic, meaning that the “similar” semantic is based on metaphor.

2. A compound word consists of a semantics formed on the basis of metonymy. For example, the main morpheme in the word **boshqotirma** (puzzle) has the semantic "mind", which is formed on the basis of the spiritual connection between the morphemes of the head and the mind.

3. The composition of a compound word consists of a sememe formed on the basis of synecdoche. For example, the word **chalabosh** means “hair that has been shaved”. The headline in the compound word meant “hair”. The words head and hair are semantically close in that they represent the semantics of “whole” and “part”.

4. A compound word consists of a semantics formed on the basis of a function. For example, the **lashkarboshi** (chief) morpheme in the words of the **yurtboshi** (leader), the word **bosh** (head) represents the semaphore of "management." On the basis of the presence of the semantic "management" in the lexemes of the person and the chief, according to the nature of the task, such compound words as army **lashkarboshi**, **yurtboshiof** state appeared.

In terms of semantic structure, seme is usually represented by a phrase, sometimes in the form of a sentence, and seme in the form of a word. Semantics in the context of a seme (whether in the form of a phrase or a sentence) is divided into two parts: subordinate semes and dominant semes [3, p. 13]. Depending on the amount of subordinate semantics, sememe is given in the form of simple and complex phrases. It will be possible to simplify complex combinations in order to express the basic meaning. When the semantics of some compound words are abbreviated in the form of a simple phrase, the morphemes of the compound word are the same as the basic semantics in the sememe, i.e., the same. For example, the semantics of the word **g‘o‘zapoya** (cotton stalk) is “the stem of a harvested cotton plant”, and a concise expression of this sememe is formed by combining the “cotton” sema in the subordinate part and the “stem” sema in the dominant part (cotton stalk). In this case, the sememe of the word **g‘o‘zapoya** (cotton stalk) is the “stem of cotton” and the morphemes and semes are similar in form and meaning. The remaining semantics of the **g‘o‘zapoya** (word cotton) (“harvest”, “harvester”, “derived”, “plant”) serve to explain the meaning of the word more fully.

It is well known that the basic concept specific to a phrase is expressed through the units in the dominant part. For example, the concept of the stem is primary in the combination of the word **bedaningpoya**, while the part of the **bedapoya** serves to represent the sign of the stem. The word **poya** refers to the sememe “the upright part of the plant that supports the branches, leaves, flowers, and fruits of a plant”. When a compound word is formed from a phrase, sometimes the second part expresses a different meaning than its own. For example, the compound word **bedapoya** means “the area where **bedapoya** is planted, cotton grows”. The **poya** part of the word **bedapoya** assumes the semantics “field” as a result of the ellipsis phenomenon (the area where the **beda** stem grows). For example: **Namozshomdabedapoyagayolg‘izbordim**. (M.Hidir, Coasts) Hence, the **poya** part of the word **bedapoya** means “planted area or growing area”. It is known that since the suffix **-zor** has

the same meaning, the stem part in the word *bedapoya* has the same meaning as the *-zor* part in the word *bedazor*. The compound word *bedapoya* is in this respect synonymous with the simple word *bedazor*.

It should be noted that certain semantics in the semantic structure are also important in the formation of compound words. For example: The following compound words are formed on the basis of semantics specific to the semantics of the word *bosh* (head) [4, p. 110]:

Seme of the word <i>bosh</i> (head)	Compound words
“kalla”	<i>boshyalang</i>
“bo‘yin”	<i>bohvoqboshvoqsiz</i>
“aql-hush”, “miya”	<i>boshqotirma</i>
“asosiy”	<i>boshariq</i>
“birinchi”, “engoldingi”	<i>boshmaldoq</i>
“odam”	<i>boshpana, boshpanasiz</i>

Typically, denotative semantics of word semantics form a lexical meaning, connotative semantics form a methodological meaning, and potential semantics form a pragmatic meaning. Semantics of compound parts of speech are formed under the influence of denotative, connotative, potential semantics. While the semantic structure of compound words such as for example, *oqqush, uchburchak* (swan, triangle) consists of denotative semantics, connotative semantics play a key role in the formation of the *betgachopar* lexeme. Compound words like *xumkalla, toshyurak* appeared through pragmatic semantics.

Compound words are formed on the basis of literal or figurative phrases. For example, the word *asalari* (bee) has a literal meaning, while *otquloq, sheryurak*, etc. have appeared on the basis of portable meanings. Also, on the basis of phrases, some of which have a portable meaning, compound words such as *karnaygul, tuyaqush, qo‘yko‘zsho‘rdanak, tomorqa* are made. It is known that word combinations are divided into two: free combinations and fixed combinations. Examples of compound words formed on the basis of free compounds are *қовунқоқи, карнайгул*, etc., and compound words formed on the basis of fixed compounds (exact expressions) are examples of words such as *boshqotirma, ichakuzdi*. The phrase *boshqotirmoq* means “to think hard, to think, to worry”. For example, *HosilYoqubovnozikroqbirnarsaustida bosh qotiribo‘tirganekan (Mushtum)*. This phrase is based on the word *boshqotirmoq*. This compound word is used to mean “riddle” The semantic side of artificial words formed on the basis of stable compounds is represented by a seme. For example, the word *ichakuzdi* means “interesting” seme.

There will be a phonetic change in the morphemes of some compound words formed on the basis of word combinations. M., sound drop in words such as *shosupa* (shohsupa), *shotut* (shohtut); there is a sound exchange in words such as *boshmaldoq* (thumb), *boshvoq* (bosh + bog‘).

A compound is also formed based on the fact that the potential semes are valence semes. On the basis of such phrases, compound words such as **tosh***yurak*, **qiltamoq** appear. For example, the word stone is associated with the word **yurak** (heart) on the basis of the "hard" seme and the emaciations characteristic of this sema that "retain their state under normal conditions, which is difficult to change." So the words **tosh** (stone) and **yurak** (heart) are connected on the basis of the "hard" classic. Therefore, the semantic structure of the compound word **tosh***yurak* has a "hard" semantics.

Thus, semema and semantics play an important role in the formation of compound words. Based on this, compound words are formed as follows:

1. Simulation semaphore: **karnaygul**, **tuyaqush**.
2. The semantics of "purposefulness": **gultuvak**, **molqo'ra**, **olovkurak**, **tokqaychi**, **qiymataxta**.
3. The semantic "belonging to a place": **suvlon**, **togolcha**, **cho'lyalpiz**.
4. "Quantity" seme: **mingoyoq**, **qirqog'ayni**.

These sememes and semantics serve to lay down the meaning of the compound word. For example, **karnaygul** (trumpet) means "trumpet-like flower", **gultuvak** means "flower-pot," and **tog'olcha** means "mountain cherry."

Some phrases and compound words consist of the same words in content. Sometimes the concepts they represent are also similar. For example, the seme of **qovunningqoqisi** (jerked melon) and **qovunqoqi** (jerked melon) units consist of the seme of "peeled and dried melon". Such units are clearly distinguished by their addition or subtraction. But the content of some compound words is written separately. For example, is a compound verb, and the antonym is formed on the basis of the addition of semantic morphemes. The part that goes is "move forward" and the part that comes is "move back". Some such compound verbs have the meaning of an action performed in succession. For example, the verb **olibkeldi** (brought) means semantically the sequential execution of the act of taking and coming [5, p.186]. The first part of these compound words does not explain the meaning of the second, in this respect it differs from the word combinations.

In summary, the compound word structure consists of language and speech units. Therefore, the semantic structure is analyzed on the basis of **sememe**, **seme**, **ema**. Lexical units are also formed on the basis of free, stable compounds and the transition of a sentence to a compound word. In this regard, word combinations, sentences, compound words are studied differently on the basis of semantic, syntactic analysis.

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